

Supplemental Figure 1: Upset plot of genes that show significant (false discovery rate adjusted p-value cutoff of 0.01) differential gene expression (DEGs) in response to heat shock across four experimental time points (x-axis) when compared to controls. The horizontal bars represent the abundance of DEGs for each timepoint. The vertical bars represent the size of the intersection between sets of DEGs for all timepoint comparisons. ($p < 0.01$)